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Assessment of Medicinal Values of Rauvolfia vomitoria (Afzel) in Ibadan Municipality

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Research Article

Assessment of Medicinal Values of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* (Afzel) in Ibadan Municipality

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ABSTRACT

Naturally inherited herbs are almost lost and only very few are left in the herbal trade. The study therefore assessed the medicinal values of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* and its availability in Ibadan municipality with the use of structured questionnaires and target informant interview. A multistage sampling procedure was used to collect data on medicinal values of *Rauvolfia vomitoria*. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and cross tabulation.

The findings revealed that *Rauvolfia vomitoria* has a lot of medical potential in curing and preventing ailments like malaria, typhoid, and jaundice among others. It also has aesthetic effects on human beings and their environment. The plant is abundant at both seasons of the year as testified by 95% of the respondents.

It is therefore recommended that sustainable management and domestication of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* must be ensured for posterity. In the same vein, preservation techniques of the harvested parts must be intensified to avoid quick spoilage.

Keywords: *Rauvolfia vomitoria*, municipality, ailments, sustainable management.

INTRODUCTION

Africa is a continent endowed with an enormous wealth of plant resources. Over 5,000 different species are known to occur in the forest regions alone, and most of them have been used for several centuries in traditional medicine for the prevention and treatment of disease (Iwu, 1993). African plant does not consist of dietetics alone, but include many potent herbs.

The use of plants for medicinal purpose had been in vogue from time immemorial. A large proportion of the medicines in use now, were developed from tropical plants (Anno; 2003a). Thus, these days' forest resources are managed for multiple goods and services, ranging from food, gum, tannin, medicine and amelioration of climate among others.

The use of traditional botanic knowledge as a promising instrument in bio prospecting of useful plants for human and animal medicine has recently increased. This results in ethnomedical and medical ethnobotanical research methods and techniques which contribute to validation and development of new plant based drugs (Slikkerveer, 2001; Quah, 2003). These have called for a review of our traditional herb especially *Rauvolfia vomitoria* which is believed to be highly medicinal.

Rauvolfia vomitoria occurs naturally in forest but is mostly found in forest regrowth where fallow periods are prolonged. *Rauvolfia vomitoria* is associated with palms, *Trema gueneensis* and *combretum* species and is one of the last species to disappear in this particular seral stage. It belongs to the family of Apocynaceae, Its common names are swizzle stick (English) and Asofeyeje (Yoruba) (Ekutudo, 2003).

Rauvolfia vomitoria is a shrub or small tree up to 8m older parts contain no latex. The branches are whorled and the nodes enlarged and lumpy leaves in threes, elliptic-acuminate to broadly lanceolate. Flowers are minute, sweet-scented; branches of inflorescences are distinctly superfluous with hardly ant free corolla lobes. Fruits are fleshy and red in colour. The generic name *Rauvolfia* commemorates a 16th century epithet *vomitoria* refers to the purgative and emetic properties of the bark (Blumenthal, 1998).

Rauvolfia vomitoria is widely planted as ornamental plant, it is used as firewood for instance in Sierra Leone. The bark yields a good fibre, and yellow dye is obtained from the bark. The seeds are used in making decorative necklaces. The sweet scent of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* flowers are frequented by bees. It is also used as timber. (Ekutudo, 2003). According to Macdonald (1986) silvicultural investigation revealed that *Rauvolfia vomitoria* can

regenerate itself successfully in its natural habitat, but no attempt has been made by the farmers to grow the tree artificially.

In Gabon, the bark and root powder of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* are mixed with water or palm oil to kill fleas and vermin. *Rauvolfia vomitoria* is used to treat leprosy in the Democratic Republic of Congo. The plant is very important and useful in the treatment of lunatic patients; the root is added to gin and given to mentally ill persons. It can also be grounded into powder and taken with pap, and can be taken in form of decoction (Fetrow et al, 1999) used for rheumatic pains. An infusion of the root bark is used to treat jaundice and gastro-intestinal disturbance.

Good health is an integral part of happy living. It is the major concern of every individual to be healthy. They therefore go about seeking for different drugs that will keep their souls and body together. But unfortunately, poor economic condition of the country has made people to fall victim of adulterated drugs. But more recently, the prevailing economic recession is pressing on the populace to accept traditional medicare because of the high cost of the orthodox drug.

Apart from this, the drugs are sold at prices, which only a fraction of the Nigeria populace can afford. It is unfortunate that the naturally inherited herbs and herbal practices are almost lost and only very few are left in the trade. Also in the same manner, most of the knowledge is being eroded as generations passed by; this therefore calls for study of medicinal values of *Rauvolfia vomitoria*

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in Ibadan metropolis, the capital city of Oyo State. It is located approximately on longitude $3^{\circ}51'$ East of the Greenwich Meridian and latitude $7^{\circ}23'1''$ North of the Equator at a distance some 145kilometres worth east of Lagos.

The total land area of the eleven Local Governments of the Ibadan metropolitan area is 3.123km^2 out of which about 15% falls in Urban Ibadan while the remaining 85% is in Rural Ibadan.

A multistage sampling procedure was used to collect data on medicinal values of *Rauvolfia vomitoria*. In the first stage of sampling, four local government areas (LGAs) out of five LGAs in Ibadan metropolis were purposively selected for the study (80% sampling intensity). These LGAs include Ibadan North, Ibadan North West, Ibadan South East and Ibadan South west local government area. As second stage of sampling, each Local Government Area was stratified into four different zones.

Purposive sampling technique was used to select a market located in four cardinal points of each Local Government Area (North, South, East and West) so as to cover socio-economic features of the study areas. In each market; Sango, Beere, Bode, and Alesinloye, 15 herb sellers were randomly selected giving a total 60 respondents for the four sample areas. Focus Group discussion and target informant interview were also employed in the data collection process. This was to obtain additional and sensitive information which people may not want to give willinly in questionnaire survey.

Descriptive and cross tabulation were used in analyzing the data and these include: percentages and frequency distribution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Availability and sources of *Rauvolfia vomitoria*

Figure 1: Bar-chart showing sources of *Rauvolfia vomitoria*

Figure 2: Bar-chart showing collection period of *Rauvolfia vomitoria*

All respondents confirm the knowledge of the plant and its parts. 48.3% of the respondents procured *Rauvolfia vomitoria* from the farmland, 51.7% from the forest and none of the respondent got it either from the garden or from the market. (Fig 1) This corroborate to findings of Etukudo (2003), that *Rauvolfia vomitoria* is more available in the forest than in the farmland. This depicts that conservation of our forest resources in general is necessary for sustainability of valuable species such as *Rauvolfia vomitoria*. Fig 2 shows that *Rauvolfia vomitoria* is not restricted to a season; it is available through out the year. This actually shows that the species is readily available for medicinal use all the time.

Socio economic information by the herb seller dealing with *Rauvolfia vomitoria*

Table 1

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Method of selling plant		
Part time	-	-
Full time basis	60	100.0
Total	60	100.0
Workers/Apprentices		
Yes	31	51.7
No	29	48.3
Total	60	100.0
Profitability		
Very profitable	40	66.7
Manageable	20	33.3
Not Profitable	-	-
Total	60	100.0
Sustainability		
Yes	60	100.0
No	-	-
Total	60	100.0
Training Experience		
By Training	18	30.0
By Adoption	42	70.0
Others	-	-
Total	60	100.0

Table 1 shows that 100% of the respondents engaged in selling *Rauvolfia vomitoria* and other herbs on fulltime basis. This implies that supplementary income is being realized from the selling of the species. This finding agrees

with (1995) that forest based activities provide supplementary sources of family income apart from agriculture and also conforms to the findings of Bayala *et al.* (2005) that households derive sustenance livelihoods from NTFPs. It was also observed that higher percentage of the respondents (66.7%) confirmed profitability of selling *Rauvolfia vomitoria* (Table 1). This therefore necessitates sustainable management of the species and other NTFPs for continuous financial sustenance of the family that engage in the business.

It was also revealed that 51.7% of the respondent had apprentices while 48.3% did not. This means that apart from inheritance, the business can also be learnt. That is why 30.0% of the respondent got into the business by training and 70.0% through adoption. This is an indication that the largest percentage got to know about the trade from their parents when they were young and so the knowledge transferred through generations. The involvement of young family member in the business indicates the posterity of the business. This is an omen for sustainable management of the species. Since the younger generation who benefit from the business will contribute to its conservation.

Table 2: Preparation and administration of different parts of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* in curing ailments

Parts	Ailments	Preparation
Leaves	1. Malaria 2. Hypertension/high blood pressure 3. Stomach-ache	Boil leaves with water before drinking by patients. Squeeze the leaves to remove the bitterness and then cook it before drinking. Squeeze the leaves and take the juice extract.
Stem	1. Malaria 2. Bareness	Boil it with water and then leave for two days to ferment before drinking it. It is cooked with some other medicinal plant i.e. concoction before taken
Root	1. Jaundice 2. Erotic dream	The root is cooked with snail The roots added to some other medicinal plants and soaked in gin for 48hours before taken
Seed	1. Measles	Ground the seed and mix with gin, rub it on the body of the patient.
Bark	1. Typhoid	Boil the bark with some other medicinal plants and soak for 2 days before taken by patients.

In the course of this study *Rauvolfia Vomitoria* was identified for the treatment of ailments and diseases as shown in table 2. These diseases include malaria, typhoid, jaundice, stomach-ache *Rauvolfia vomitoria* can cure ailment such as skin rashes, hypertension and measles. The findings on medicinal values of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* conforms to findings of i (2008) Kutalek and Prinz (2007) and Sharma (2004) that *Rauvolfia vomitoria* is used for the treatment of many ailments in tropical Africa.

CONCLUSION

The results of the study provide information on the medicinal value of *Rauvolfia vomitoria*. It was observed that all parts of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* have a lot of medicinal values such as curing of ailments like malaria, typhoid, and jaundice among others. Also it has protective, aesthetic and sociological effects on human being and their environments. The medicinal potential of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* revealed from the study will help to preserve our cultural medicinal heritage and its impact will invariably be useful for the future development of our traditional medicine. It is therefore recommended that sustainable management and domestication of *Rauvolfia vomitoria* must be ensured for posterity. In the same vein, preservation techniques of the harvested parts must be intensified to avoid quick spoilage.

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